

Rethinking Justice. A Systematic Review of Theories, Frameworks, and Southern Realities

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Abstract

This article presents a systematic review of justice theories and their applications within development discourse, with particular attention to Global South contexts. Drawing on literature from the humanities and social sciences, including feminist, decolonial, environmental, and perspectives from socio-legal studies, the article traces the evolution of justice from classical and liberal paradigms to contemporary frameworks such as the capability approach, recognition theory, epistemic justice, climate justice, and digital justice. Using PRISMA guidelines and a structured coding matrix, the review synthesises over two decades of scholarship, identifying how justice is variably conceptualised, as fairness, redistribution, recognition, relationality, or repair. A central argument of the article is that mainstream development approaches often rely on liberal and procedural conceptions of justice that overlook structural inequalities, historical harms, and epistemic exclusions. The review foregrounds alternative perspectives emerging from feminist, indigenous, and decolonial scholarship, which advocate for justice as transformation, plurality, and situated praxis. Empirical illustrations from land reform, gender empowerment, climate adaptation, and digital inclusion reveal the tensions between justice in theory and practice. The article concludes by identifying key knowledge gaps in the justice literature, particularly the neglect of Southern ontologies, historical responsibility, and non-textual epistemologies, and outlines emerging directions for a more grounded, plural, and transformative approach to justice in development studies. The review affirms the need to move from distributive and technocratic models to relational, reparative, and participatory forms of justice, especially in postcolonial and climate-vulnerable settings. It offers a conceptual foundation for scholars, practitioners, and policymakers committed to rethinking justice as a collective and ethical development imperative.

Keywords: *Justice; Development; Epistemic Justice; Global South; Decolonial Theory; Feminist Perspectives; Climate Justice; Digital Justice; Structural Inequality; Participatory Development*

1. Introduction

Justice remains one of the most enduring and contested concepts in human thought. Its importance extends across the humanities and social sciences. It is examined through legal traditions as well as socio-legal, political-theoretical, and cultural perspectives. In classical philosophy, justice was associated with virtue and social harmony (Plato, trans. 2000), while in liberal political theory, it became primarily associated with fairness and rational procedures, most famously in Rawls' (1971) *A Theory of Justice*, which laid the groundwork for much of contemporary political philosophy. In Rawls' formulation, justice is a matter of ensuring fairness through impartial rules, equality of opportunity, and the protection of basic liberties.

Habermas (1996), by contrast, reconceptualised justice as the outcome of democratic deliberation within the public sphere. From his discourse ethics perspective, norms are just if and only

if they can secure the rational assent of all those affected under conditions of free and non-coercive communication. Rather than grounding justice in abstract principles, Habermas situates it in the procedures of inclusive dialogue, where legitimacy arises from the participation of equal citizens in deliberative processes. Yet, while Rawls has been criticised for abstracting from historical and structural inequalities, Habermas' model has been faulted for its formalism, insofar as it presupposes the possibility of equal participation in deliberative processes despite persistent power asymmetries. Such limitations have led theorists to call for more context-sensitive and relational understandings of justice (Young, 2000, Fraser, 2009).

In response to these critiques, the concept of justice has undergone significant evolution. Scholars such as Sen (2009) and Nussbaum (2011) introduced the capability approach, arguing that justice should focus on what people are actually able to do and to be, not merely on the distribution of goods. Meanwhile, Fraser (2009) advanced a tripartite model of justice, encompassing redistribution, recognition, and representation, arguing that justice must simultaneously confront economic inequality, cultural misrecognition, and political marginalisation. This framework provides a more comprehensive lens for analysing the multiple and intersecting axes of injustice in contemporary societies.

While these debates have enriched theoretical understandings, justice in development discourse remains unevenly theorised. In many instances, development frameworks adopt a narrowly distributive conception of justice, emphasising resource allocation without adequately engaging with historical injustices, epistemic hierarchies, or participatory exclusion (Schlosberg, 2007; Robeyns, 2005). This tendency is particularly problematic in contexts shaped by colonial legacies and structural dependency, where liberal-democratic assumptions may not resonate with local conceptions of fairness, autonomy, and repair (de Sousa Santos, 2014; Fanon, 1963).

Indeed, critical and decolonial scholars have pointed out that the global discourse on justice continues to marginalise non-Western ontologies and epistemologies. For example, Sousa Santos (2014) argues that dominant models of justice often commit "epistemicide" by excluding indigenous and Southern knowledge systems. Earlier, Fanon (1963) had framed justice in terms of decolonial struggle, contending that true justice requires structural rupture and reparative transformation. These perspectives challenge the presumed neutrality of mainstream justice frameworks and demand a more pluriversal approach (Escobar, 2008; Mignolo & Walsh, 2018).

In recent years, further complexity has been added by the emergence of new domains of justice, including climate justice (Schlosberg & Collins, 2014), digital justice (Heeks, 2021), gender justice (Cornwall & Rivas, 2015), and epistemic justice (Fricker, 2007). These frameworks draw attention to the multiple, overlapping forms of injustice experienced in the Global South and highlight the inadequacy of "one-size-fits-all" development models.

Against this backdrop, this article seeks to critically examine the concept of justice through a systematic review of scholarly literature, with the aim of clarifying its theoretical foundations, dominant and alternative frameworks, and its application in development contexts, especially in the Global South. This is particularly important for the *Commons, Justice and Development Journal (CJDJ)*, whose mission includes not only academic rigour but also contextual sensitivity and transformative relevance.

The objective of this article is to map and synthesise key strands of academic literature that shape how justice is understood, framed, and operationalised in development studies. It seeks to provide conceptual clarity while recognising the diversity of interpretations and the tensions among them. To this end, the article addresses the following questions:

1. How has the concept of *Justice* been theorised within humanities and social science approaches, from classical traditions to contemporary perspectives?
2. What frameworks of justice dominate development discourse, and what alternatives have emerged from critical and Southern scholarship?
3. In what ways is justice operationalised in development interventions, policies, and struggles in the Global South?
4. What critiques, silences, or emerging directions challenge conventional understandings of justice in development?

This contribution employs a systematic literature review methodology, drawing on the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines (Page et al., 2021). The search strategy included peer-reviewed academic sources published between 2000 and 2025, retrieved from Google Scholar, Scopus, JSTOR, and Web of Science. Seminal earlier works were included for historical anchoring (e.g., Rawls, Habermas, Fanon, Fraser).

The inclusion criteria focused on works that present or critique conceptual frameworks of justice, apply justice concepts in empirical development contexts, engage with the Global South either geographically, epistemologically, or politically.

Sources were coded using a matrix aligned with the four research questions. Codes included justice type (distributive, procedural, epistemic, etc.), regional focus, methodological approach, and epistemological orientation (e.g., liberal, critical, feminist, decolonial). This enabled comparative analysis and thematic synthesis.

This article contributes to the literature in three main ways. First, it offers a structured synthesis of diverse justice theories, highlighting both their points of convergence and irreconcilability. Second, it centres perspectives from the Global South, thereby addressing the epistemic imbalance in mainstream development discourse. Third, it outlines emerging paradigms, such as restorative, climate, and digital justice, that point toward more inclusive and responsive approaches.

The article is structured as follows. Section 2 surveys the theoretical foundations and evolution of justice. Section 3 explores justice in development practice, especially in the Global South. Section 4 examines contemporary critiques and emerging paradigms. Section 5 identifies gaps and future directions for justice-focused research. Section 6 concludes with implications for scholarship and policy engagement within CJDJ.

In a world marked by intersecting crises, ecological, epistemic, economic, rethinking justice is no longer an academic luxury but a developmental necessity. This review affirms that justice must be approached not only as fairness or distribution but as historically informed, structurally aware, and epistemically plural.

2. Theoretical Foundations and Evolution of Justice

The concept of justice has traversed a long intellectual trajectory, evolving through diverse philosophical traditions, socio-political contexts, and disciplinary frameworks. From classical antiquity to modern legal systems and contemporary political theory, justice has been approached through multiple lenses, distributive, procedural, retributive, restorative, epistemic, and more recently, climate and digital justice (Schlosberg, 2007; Fraser, 2009; Heeks, 2021). This section maps the theoretical evolution of justice, identifying the dominant paradigms and their critiques, and highlighting the growing recognition of alternative frameworks emerging from the Global South.

Justice was conceptualised early in Western thought as an organising principle of society. Plato's vision of justice in *The Republic* posited a hierarchical harmony wherein each class performs its natural role (Plato, trans. 2000). Aristotle, in contrast, provided a more nuanced view by distinguishing distributive and corrective justice, the former being concerned with proportionate allocation and the latter with restoration of balance following a wrong (Aristotle, trans. 2009). In modern times, liberal philosophy redefined justice around the principles of individual rights, equality, and neutrality. John Rawls' (1971) *A Theory of Justice* became the cornerstone of this tradition. Rawls introduced the notion of "justice as fairness," formulated through the "original position" and "veil of ignorance," ensuring impartiality in designing social arrangements. His two principles, equal basic liberties and social/economic inequalities arranged to benefit the least advantaged, provided a framework that has dominated Anglo-American political philosophy for decades. However, Rawls' model has been widely criticised for its abstraction from historical injustice, identity-based exclusion, and structural inequality (Young, 1990). Critics argue that by focusing on idealised conditions, Rawls' theory sidesteps the real-world legacies of colonialism, patriarchy, and capitalism that shape access to rights and resources.

In response to the limitations of resource-based and contractarian models, Amartya Sen (2009) developed the capability approach, which reorients justice toward expanding people's actual freedoms, their capabilities to lead lives they have reason to value. Unlike Rawls' emphasis on institutional design, Sen's model is comparative and practical, aimed at reducing tangible injustice. Building on Sen's work, Martha Nussbaum (2011) articulated a list of central human capabilities that should be protected by all just societies. These include bodily health, education, political participation, and affiliation. Her approach blends normative ethics with constitutional guarantees, bridging theory and policy in areas such as gender equality, disability rights, and social protection. The capability approach has become influential in development policy (Robeyns, 2005). However, it has also been critiqued for its individualistic tendencies and for not sufficiently addressing power relations or collective agency, especially in postcolonial and indigenous contexts where justice may be more communally conceived (Gasper, 2007).

From a critical theory perspective, justice cannot be reduced to distributions or individual freedoms alone; it must also address cultural recognition and democratic participation. Nancy Fraser (2009) proposes a three-dimensional theory of justice, redistribution, recognition, and representation, which together form the necessary conditions for parity of participation. She argues that justice requires not only fair economic structures, but also the dismantling of institutionalised patterns of cultural domination and political exclusion. Fraser's model has been particularly useful in analysing intersectional injustices, such as those experienced by racialised women, indigenous peoples, and working-class migrants, groups that suffer both material deprivation and symbolic misrecognition (Fraser & Honneth, 2003). This multidimensional framing has made Fraser's work a key reference in justice studies that attempt to bridge class, identity, and governance. Nonetheless, some scholars note that Fraser's theory, while more inclusive than Rawls', remains grounded in a Euro-American political ontology, and may not sufficiently account for non-liberal or communal understandings of justice that are prevalent in many Global South contexts (de Sousa Santos, 2014).

Postcolonial and decolonial theorists have argued that conventional justice theories systematically exclude the histories, knowledges, and worldviews of formerly colonised peoples. Frantz Fanon (1963), writing from the perspective of anti-colonial resistance, framed justice as a demand for structural transformation through reparative rupture. For Fanon, justice is inseparable from liberation, it is not a distributional question but a matter of decolonising the human condition. Over the past three decades, postcolonial legal thought has evolved from a language framed by the histories and interests of nation-states, primarily focused on the dialectic between colonising and colonised nations, to a vision more attuned to the relations between the global North and the global South. This shift has made it possible to broaden the analytical lens and to rethink contemporary legal

subjectivities, moving beyond the West versus non-West dichotomy and recognising new forms of colonialism, such as the colonisation of East Timor by Indonesia, Eritrea by Ethiopia, and the occupation of Palestinian territories by Israel. Finally, it also takes into account neocolonial practices exercised by both Western and non-Western nations, which impose economic and political power, or forms of “soft imperialism,” over sites previously subjected to colonial control (Darian-Smith, 2013). Boaventura de Sousa Santos (2014) also advances the idea of *epistemic justice*, calling for the decolonisation of knowledge systems alongside political institutions. He argues that modern legal and political structures commit “epistemicide” by disqualifying non-Western ways of knowing, such as indigenous jurisprudence or African communitarian ethics, and thus justice requires a *pluriversal* politics. Similarly, Miranda Fricker (2007) highlights forms of *epistemic injustice*, where marginalised groups are wronged as knowers, either through testimonial exclusion or hermeneutical gaps, an approach increasingly applied to development contexts in which local knowledge is sidelined by technocratic models. Together, decolonial and epistemic justice frameworks compel a profound rethinking of justice, not as a normative abstraction but as a historically embedded, relational, and epistemologically inclusive endeavour (Escobar, 2008; Mignolo & Walsh, 2018).

Theorising justice has also expanded into new domains shaped by globalisation and technological change. Climate justice seeks to link environmental sustainability with fairness across and within nations. It highlights how those least responsible for environmental degradation, often marginalised communities in the Global South, bear the greatest burden of its consequences (Schlosberg & Collins, 2014). This domain demands justice not only in terms of emissions reduction, but also in adaptive capacity, procedural inclusion, and intergenerational responsibility. Digital justice has emerged in response to the growing role of data and algorithms in shaping social outcomes. Scholars like Heeks (2021) argue that many forms of digital inclusion in the Global South are actually adverse incorporations, where access does not lead to empowerment but to new forms of surveillance or precarity. Similarly, Kasirzadeh (2022) explores how algorithmic systems can entrench existing structural injustices unless evaluated through a feminist and anti-oppressive lens. These emerging frameworks reaffirm that justice today must go beyond redistributive logics. It must contend with asymmetries of voice, knowledge, and agency, particularly as they manifest in technological, ecological, and intercultural spaces.

3. Justice in Development Practice

While theoretical formulations of justice have proliferated across disciplines, their translation into development practice remains uneven and contested. Development agendas frequently invoke the language of justice, particularly social, economic, and environmental justice, yet these invocations often lack conceptual clarity or fail to engage with the structural causes of injustice in the Global South (Uvin, 2007; Hickey & du Toit, 2007). This section examines how justice is applied in development interventions, policies, and localised struggles, focusing on land reform, gender empowerment, adaptive capacity to climate change, and digital inclusion, among other domains. It also highlights the role of grassroots actors and epistemic communities in reshaping development to foreground justice as a lived and contested reality.

Access to land remains a cornerstone of justice in many agrarian societies, particularly in Africa, Asia, and Latin America. As José Carlos Mariátegui (1928/2007) powerfully articulated, anchoring social struggle in its material context: “The problem of the Indian is the problem of the land”. Land is not only a productive asset but also a symbol of identity, spiritual connection, and political autonomy (Borras & Franco, 2010). In contexts marked by colonial dispossession and postcolonial elite capture, land reform has often been framed as a mechanism for redistributive justice. However, the outcomes have been mixed. In Namibia, for instance, post-independence land reform programmes aimed at correcting apartheid-era injustices have had limited success due to reliance on the willing-seller,

willing-buyer principle and a focus on formal titling, which often favoured commercial elites over historically marginalised communities (Werner & Odendaal, 2010). Similar patterns are evident in South Africa, where land restitution has largely failed to secure sustainable livelihoods or equitable land use (Hall, 2004). These examples illustrate the gap between justice as intention and justice as outcome. While redistribution is vital, without attention to power relations, institutional dynamics, and local agency, justice interventions risk reinforcing inequality under the guise of reform (Lund, 2011).

The integration of gender justice into development discourse has been one of the most visible shifts in recent decades, particularly through frameworks such as gender mainstreaming, women's empowerment, and rights-based approaches (Cornwall & Rivas, 2015). Yet critiques abound regarding the instrumentalisation of gender in ways that prioritise economic outcomes over structural transformation. For example, microcredit programmes and entrepreneurship initiatives targeting women have been celebrated for their potential to "lift women out of poverty," but often rely on neoliberal logics of individual responsibility, while failing to dismantle patriarchal systems that restrict access to property, credit, or political representation (Kabeer, 2005; Chant & Sweetman, 2012). Moreover, these interventions frequently ignore intersectional dynamics, such as caste, ethnicity, or disability, which shape women's experiences of injustice in complex ways (Crenshaw, 1991). In contrast, feminist development scholars and activists argue for a transformative gender justice framework that includes bodily autonomy, unpaid care work, political voice, and cultural recognition as essential components of justice (Sen & Mukherjee, 2014). Such approaches centre collective action, solidarity economies, and decolonial feminist ethics as paths toward more just futures.

Justice in development has taken on renewed urgency in the context of climate change, which disproportionately affects low-income, resource-dependent, and historically marginalised communities (Schlosberg & Collins, 2014). The notion of climate justice highlights the uneven distribution of both responsibility and vulnerability: while the Global North accounts for the majority of historical emissions, the Global South bears the brunt of climate-induced displacement, droughts, and crop failure. Yet many climate adaptation projects in the South, such as afforestation, biofuel plantations, or carbon offset schemes, have led to new forms of land grabbing, displacement, and resource enclosure (Fairhead, Leach, & Scoones, 2012). In Mozambique, for instance, REDD+ projects aimed at reducing emissions have reportedly excluded local communities from decision-making while restricting their customary land use (Saté & Watson, 2018). Similarly, in Namibia, the Hyphen Hydrogen Energy project has raised concerns over both ecological and social justice: by allocating a large portion of the Tsau//Khaeb National Park to green hydrogen and ammonia production, it risks undermining local stewardship practices while placing additional pressure on an ecosystem already threatened by climate change (Venditto & Kamwanyah, 2025). These cases challenge the notion that sustainability and justice are automatically aligned. Environmental justice frameworks argue that genuine climate justice must include procedural equity (inclusive decision-making), distributional fairness (equal access to resources and protection), and recognitional justice (valuing indigenous and local knowledges) (Agyeman et al., 2016; Whyte, 2016). Indigenous movements across the Americas and Africa have increasingly mobilised around territorial sovereignty, cosmovision, and land-ancestor to assert alternative visions of justice that transcend Western legal frameworks (Escobar, 2008).

As digital technologies become central to service delivery, education, finance, and governance, the question of digital justice has gained prominence. While digital inclusion has been framed as a development goal, critics argue that many "inclusive" models produce adverse incorporation, where marginalised populations gain access only on unequal or exploitative terms (Heeks, 2021). For example, biometric ID systems such as Aadhaar in India have improved service delivery for some, but have also excluded vulnerable groups from food rations and healthcare due to data errors, lack of access, or surveillance concerns (Drèze, 2016). The Indian Supreme Court in *Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) v. Union of India* (2018) acknowledged these risks of exclusion and vulnerability, yet nonetheless upheld

Aadhaar's constitutionality as a tool for welfare delivery, framing technical deficiencies as a matter for government resolution. This illustrates how legal frameworks may legitimise digital systems while leaving structural injustices unaddressed, underscoring that digital development must be evaluated not only in terms of access but also in terms of agency, consent, and control. Justice in the digital age requires attention to algorithmic fairness, data sovereignty, and inclusive digital citizenship, particularly for women, rural populations, and indigenous groups (Eubanks, 2018; Noble, 2018). Such perspectives advocate for co-designed technologies, public oversight, and technological pluralism as principles of justice.

Across the Global South, grassroots movements have asserted their own visions of justice, often rooted in lived experiences, historical grievances, and spiritual or ecological ethics. Examples include the Landless Workers' Movement in Brazil (MST – Movimento dos Trabalhadores Rurais Sem Terra), the Shack Dwellers' Movement in South Africa (Abahlali baseMjondolo), pastoralist federations in Kenya and women's cooperatives in India.

These movements challenge both the content and the procedures of mainstream development. They demand not just material redistribution, but also voice, recognition, and control over knowledge production (Tandon, 2008; Santos, 2014). Participatory development has long been proposed as a corrective mechanism, yet in practice, participation often becomes tokenistic or externally defined (Cooke & Kothari, 2001). For this reason, it is crucial for grassroots movements and initiatives to define their own terrain for practicing participation in concrete terms, which also entails co-creating norms and governance structures through which they can self-organize. This constitutes a key node in the grammar of the commons, both in a theoretical sense (Ostrom, 1990) and in the construction of 'spaces of alternatives' (Micciarelli & D'Andrea). Emerging models of transformative participation, such as co-production, community-led monitoring, and participatory budgeting, aim to embed justice in decision-making itself (Gaventa & Barrett, 2012). These approaches redefine justice not as an outcome to be delivered, but as a process to be collectively shaped.

4. Contemporary Debates and Critiques

Despite its widespread use in development discourse, the concept of justice remains contested, fragmented, and often depoliticised. While liberal and procedural frameworks have shaped mainstream approaches, a growing body of scholarship and activism highlights their limitations in addressing the complex realities of injustice, particularly in the Global South. This section explores four key critiques of dominant justice paradigms: (1) the liberal-paradigmatic bias of development justice, (2) feminist and intersectional perspectives, (3) decolonial and epistemic critiques, and (4) justice in a planetary and technological age.

One of the most enduring critiques is the liberal bias that undergirds dominant theories of justice in development. Rooted in Enlightenment notions of individual autonomy, impartiality, and rationality, liberal justice frameworks tend to prioritise procedural fairness and resource distribution over structural transformation or collective agency (Young, 1990; Hickey & Mohan, 2004). As such, they often assume a neutral state, universal legal norms, and a separation between ethics and politics. Critics argue that this liberal framing obscures systemic power relations, historical legacies of violence, and the political nature of redistribution. For instance, Uvin (2007) contends that justice initiatives that fail to engage with power dynamics, especially in post-conflict or postcolonial settings, risk reinforcing elite dominance under the guise of impartiality. Similarly, Fraser (2009) warns that redistribution without recognition or representation results in shallow or unstable justice. Moreover, the proceduralism of liberal justice may misrecognise the ontologies of communities that do not separate legal from spiritual or ecological orders. This is particularly salient in African and indigenous settings, where justice is often embedded in relationality, reciprocity, and communal obligations (Murithi, 2006; Wiredu, 1996). From

a sociological standpoint, Reza Banakar (2011) similarly foregrounds the normativity of law as rooted in lived experience, engaging with plural normative orders and moving beyond the modernist rationality of Western legality.

Feminist scholars have long challenged justice theories that treat individuals as disembodied, genderless subjects. Building on critiques of Rawlsian liberalism and its gender-blind neutrality, feminist theorists argue that justice must account for socially constructed identities, embodied experience, and relational care ethics (Tronto, 1993; Nussbaum, 2000). Intersectionality, a term coined by Crenshaw (1991), provides a lens through which to examine how overlapping identities, such as race, gender, class, caste, and disability, shape experiences of injustice. Therefore, intersectionality functions as a counter to essentialism, exposing the law's reliance on fixed categories that can obscure or misrepresent particular forms of discrimination (Samuels, 2013). On this basis, intersectional justice demands more than equal treatment; it calls for recognition of multiple axes of oppression and the differentiated impact of development interventions. This critique is especially relevant to development programmes that target "women" as a homogenous group while neglecting intra-group differences. For example, gender empowerment projects often focus on economic inclusion (e.g., microcredit) but ignore structural issues such as unpaid care work, intimate partner violence, and lack of bodily autonomy (Cornwall & Rivas, 2015; Chant, 2008). Feminist justice also emphasises the relational dimension of well-being, challenging the atomised view of rights and entitlements. In this view, justice involves nurturing the conditions of interdependence, dignity, and emotional and ecological care, domains often neglected in mainstream development frameworks (Held, 2006; Federici, 2011).

Perhaps the most profound contemporary critique of justice in development arises from decolonial thought, which challenges the epistemic, ontological, and historical foundations of Eurocentric justice models. Decolonial scholars argue that modern conceptions of justice have been deeply implicated in colonial conquest, racial capitalism, and the exclusion of non-Western worldviews (Fanon, 1963; Mignolo, 2011; de Sousa Santos, 2014). Epistemic injustice, the marginalisation of certain knowledge systems, voices, and modes of knowing, is now recognised as a critical form of development injustice. As Fricker (2007) explains, epistemic injustice occurs when individuals are discredited as knowers or lack the conceptual resources to articulate their experiences. This is common in development contexts where donor agencies privilege technocratic indicators over lived knowledge, or where indigenous knowledge is appropriated without consent or recognition (Escobar, 2008). Justice, from a decolonial perspective, requires pluriversality, the co-existence and mutual respect of multiple knowledges and ways of being (Mignolo & Walsh, 2018). This includes recognising indigenous legal orders, communal property regimes, and relational cosmologies not as relics of the past, but as living systems of justice with contemporary relevance. Furthermore, decolonial critique underscores that justice must be reparative. It must address historical harms not only through symbolic recognition but also through material restitution, structural transformation, and memory work. Examples include land back movements, cultural revival initiatives, and decolonial education reforms (Tuck & Yang, 2012; Dussel, 2008; Beristain, 2024).

Recent scholarship has expanded the justice discourse into new frontiers, including climate, planetary, and digital realms. These emerging paradigms argue that traditional justice frameworks, rooted in anthropocentrism, territorial sovereignty, and economic redistribution, are ill-equipped to address the trans-scalar, intergenerational, and technological challenges of our time. Climate justice demands an ethical and political response to the unequal burdens of environmental degradation. Schlosberg and Collins (2014) argue that climate justice must include not only distributive aspects but also procedural and recognitional components, particularly in relation to indigenous communities, small island nations, and women farmers disproportionately affected by climate shocks. Similarly, the digital revolution has introduced new forms of injustice related to surveillance, data extraction, algorithmic bias, and exclusion from digital citizenship (Eubanks, 2018; Noble, 2018). Heeks (2021)

proposes a digital justice framework that critiques “adverse incorporation” into digital systems, where marginalised populations gain access under inequitable conditions, reinforcing existing hierarchies. These critiques call for an expansion of justice frameworks to include concepts such as data sovereignty, intergenerational rights, and planetary relationality, terms that foreground not only what is just for humans, but what sustains all life systems across time and space (Whyte, 2018; Kimmerer, 2013).

In summary, contemporary critiques have transformed the justice conversation from one focused narrowly on allocation and rights to one that is deeply historical, relational, intersectional, and epistemically plural. They compel a shift from procedural fairness to transformative justice, a justice that dismantles structural oppression, centres lived experience, and cultivates new ways of knowing and being. In the next section, we explore the knowledge gaps and emerging directions that could shape a more grounded and radical justice scholarship in development.

5. Knowledge Gaps and Emerging Directions

While the scholarship on justice in development has become more diverse, critical, and interdisciplinary, important gaps remain in how justice is theorised, implemented, and evaluated, particularly in relation to the historical legacies, epistemic hierarchies, and contextual complexities of the Global South. This section identifies key limitations in the literature and proposes emerging directions for more transformative and grounded engagements with justice in development studies.

A persistent gap in development discourse is the emphasis on justice as an outcome, often measured through distributive indicators such as income, land, or services, with insufficient attention to justice as a process. This instrumentalist framing tends to obscure the procedural and relational dimensions of justice, including voice, participation, and trust (Young, 1990; Sen, 2009).

While participatory development models have aimed to bridge this gap, many fall short of genuine inclusion due to tokenism, elite capture, or externally driven agendas (Cooke & Kothari, 2001; Gaventa & Barrett, 2012). There is need for frameworks that embed justice throughout the policy and project cycle, not only in end goals but also in agenda setting, deliberation, and accountability mechanisms.

Much of the literature and practice continues to treat justice as ahistorical, focusing on immediate inequalities without addressing the deep structural and historical roots of marginalisation, including colonial dispossession, racialisation, and patriarchal social orders (Fraser, 2009; Fanon, 1963). As Mamdani (1996) argues, postcolonial states often reproduce colonial logics of rule through indirect governance, exclusionary citizenship, and elite brokerage, factors that any justice-focused development agenda must confront.

Yet few justice frameworks in development incorporate historical responsibility, intergenerational harm, or transitional justice into their analysis. This is a critical omission, particularly in societies grappling with legacies of genocide, slavery, apartheid, or state collapse. Emerging work on reparative and memorial justice suggests new directions for integrating historical consciousness into development planning (de Greiff, 2006; Tuck & Yang, 2012).

Despite the growing influence of epistemic justice in critical theory, development studies still lag behind in theorising and applying this concept (Fricker, 2007; de Sousa Santos, 2014). Development interventions often rely on technocratic expertise, external evaluation logics, and a narrow set of “evidence-based” methods that marginalise local knowledges, oral traditions, and experiential narratives (Escobar, 2008).

There is a lack of systematic inquiry into how knowledge production, validation, and policy translation exclude subaltern perspectives, particularly in areas such as education reform, health systems design, or environmental assessment. More work is needed to integrate decolonial methodologies, co-production of knowledge, and pluralist evaluation frameworks into development practice (Smith, 2012; Chambers, 2014).

Although climate, digital, and algorithmic justice have been addressed in adjacent literatures, their integration into mainstream development studies remains limited. For instance, development planning often overlooks climate vulnerability as a justice issue, treating it as a technical problem rather than a consequence of global inequalities (Roberts & Parks, 2007; Schlosberg & Collins, 2014).

Likewise, digital development agendas tend to prioritise infrastructure and access, without addressing algorithmic bias, data colonialism, or surveillance risks (Eubanks, 2018; Heeks, 2021). These domains require the development of new conceptual vocabularies, policy tools, and participatory safeguards that respond to the socio-technical complexities of 21st-century development.

Although the Global South is often the site of justice interventions, the theoretical frameworks that guide these interventions remain disproportionately anchored in Northern institutions and philosophical traditions (Kohn, 2019; Mignolo & Walsh, 2018). While postcolonial and indigenous scholars have offered robust critiques, their work is still underrepresented in leading journals, curricula, and policy dialogues.

There is a clear need to amplify Southern theorising, including African philosophy (Wiredu, 1996; Mbembe, 2001), Latin American *buen vivir* (Gudynas, 2011), and Asian relational ethics (Kim, 2018), not as case studies but as generative sources of theory. This also includes recognising non-textual epistemologies, ritual, song, embodied memory, as valid forms of justice knowledge.

Building on these gaps, several emerging directions point toward a more robust and contextually grounded justice research agenda:

1. Justice as Transformation: Moving beyond reformist approaches toward those that aim to restructure power, institutions, and imaginaries (Fraser, 2009; Santos, 2014).
2. Justice as Plurality: Recognising multiple, coexisting notions of justice that reflect cultural, spiritual, and ecological differences (Mignolo & Walsh, 2018; Whyte, 2016).
3. Justice as Situated Praxis: Grounding justice in the lived experiences, struggles, and knowledge systems of affected communities (Chambers, 2014; Tandon, 2008).
4. Justice as Memory and Repair: Linking development with historical accountability, reparative action, and cultural healing (de Greiff, 2006; Fanon, 1963).
5. Justice as Planetary Ethics: Expanding justice frameworks to address non-human agency, intergenerational rights, and planetary stewardship (Schlosberg, 2013; Kimmerer, 2013).

These directions suggest that future scholarship must be more intersectional, interdisciplinary, and intercultural, engaging seriously with grassroots perspectives, Southern epistemologies, and alternative modes of development that reframe justice not as a technical deliverable, but as a collective ethical practice.

6. Conclusion

This article set out to rethink the concept of justice through a systematic review of scholarly literature across philosophy, socio-legal studies, political theory and development studies. It aimed to clarify the theoretical foundations, identify dominant and alternative frameworks, assess real-world

applications in development practice, and foreground critiques and knowledge gaps, particularly from Global South perspectives. The review reveals that justice is not a monolithic or universally agreed concept, but rather a contested and evolving terrain that reflects deep disagreements about fairness, recognition, power, and the very meaning of a good society.

The review began by tracing the theoretical evolution of justice from classical and liberal foundations to contemporary critiques. While Rawlsian liberalism remains influential for its focus on fairness and institutional design (Rawls, 1971), alternative models such as the capability approach (Sen, 2009; Nussbaum, 2011) and Fraser's three-dimensional theory (2009) offer more context-sensitive and multidimensional lenses. These frameworks expand the scope of justice to include recognition, representation, and freedom to flourish, while exposing the limitations of purely procedural or distributive paradigms. Section 3 demonstrated how justice frameworks are operationalised, often problematically, in development practice. Whether in land reform, gender empowerment, climate adaptation, or digital inclusion, efforts to promote justice frequently fall short due to technical rationalism, elite capture, and historical amnesia. While distributive justice is central to many development goals, it is rarely accompanied by structural reform or genuine community participation. Grassroots movements, however, are offering powerful models of participatory and reparative justice, often grounded in indigenous, feminist, or spiritual traditions that challenge Western-centric approaches (Escobar, 2008; Santos, 2014). Section 4 mapped contemporary critiques that expose the shortcomings of liberal neutrality, the inadequacy of mainstream gender frameworks, and the epistemic violence of colonial knowledge systems. Feminist theorists demand justice that recognises embodied experience and intersectional oppression (Crenshaw, 1991; Tronto, 1993), while decolonial scholars call for justice that is pluriversal, reparative, and relational (Fanon, 1963; Mignolo & Walsh, 2018). Climate and digital justice discourses further expand the field, insisting that justice must now contend with planetary ethics, technological sovereignty, and intergenerational rights (Whyte, 2016; Heeks, 2021). Section 5 identified knowledge gaps and emerging directions. The literature still leans heavily on Northern theories, often sidelining Southern ontologies and non-textual epistemologies. It remains weak on historical responsibility, epistemic co-production, and justice as a lived praxis. Promising future directions include theories of justice that are transformative rather than reformist, plural rather than universal, and ethically embedded rather than institutionally abstract. Such approaches encourage a shift from "delivering justice" to co-creating just worlds with those most affected by injustice.

Ultimately, rethinking justice means recognising that injustice is not accidental, but structured, and that justice is not merely a distributive formula, but a relational, historical, and collective endeavour. It means moving from justice as abstraction to justice as solidarity, from fairness just as procedure to fairness as emancipation, and from development as intervention to development as co-liberation.

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References

- Banakar, R. (2011). The sociology of law: From industrialisation to globalisation. *Sociopedia.isa*, University of Westminster School of Law Research Paper No. 11-03. <https://doi.org/10.1177/205684601134>
- Beristain, C.M. (2024). *ENOMEME GOPOKIMONI. Informe sobre una perspectiva psicosocial y comunitaria del cumplimiento de la decisión de la consulta ciudadana y dictamen de la Corte Constitucional sobre el cierre de las explotaciones del ITT en el Parque Yasuni*. Acción Ecológica
- Chambers, R. (2014). *Into the unknown: Explorations in development practice*. Practical Action Publishing.
- Chant, S. (2008). The 'feminisation of poverty' and the 'feminisation' of anti-poverty programmes: Room for revision? *The Journal of Development Studies*, 44(2), 165–197. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220380701789810>
- Cooke, B., & Kothari, U. (Eds.). (2001). *Participation: The new tyranny?* Zed Books.
- Cornwall, A., & Rivas, A. M. (2015). From 'gender equality and women's empowerment' to global justice: Reclaiming a transformative agenda for gender and development. *Third World Quarterly*, 36(2), 396–415. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2015.1013341>
- Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the margins: Intersectionality, identity politics, and violence against women of color. *Stanford Law Review*, 43(6), 1241–1299. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>
- Darian-Smith, E. (2013). Postcolonial Theories of Law. In Banakar, R., & Travers, M. (Eds.). *Law and Social Theory*. Hart Publishing.
- de Greiff, P. (Ed.). (2006). *The handbook of reparations*. Oxford University Press.
- de Sousa Santos, B. (2014). *Epistemologies of the South: Justice against epistemicide*. Routledge.
- Dussel, E. (2008). *Twenty theses on politics*. Duke University Press.
- Escobar, A. (2008). *Territories of difference: Place, movements, life, redes*. Duke University Press.
- Eubanks, V. (2018). *Automating inequality: How high-tech tools profile, police, and punish the poor*. St. Martin's Press.
- Fanon, F. (1963). *The wretched of the earth* (C. Farrington, Trans.). Grove Press.
- Federici, S. (2011). *Revolution at point zero: Housework, reproduction, and feminist struggle*. PM Press.
- Fraser, N. (2009). *Scales of justice: Reimagining political space in a globalizing world*. Polity Press.
- Fricke, M. (2007). *Epistemic injustice: Power and the ethics of knowing*. Oxford University Press.
- Gaventa, J., & Barrett, G. (2012). Mapping the outcomes of citizen engagement. *World Development*, 40(12), 2399–2410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2012.05.014>

- Gudynas, E. (2011). Buen Vivir: Today's tomorrow. *Development*, 54(4), 441–447.
<https://doi.org/10.1057/dev.2011.86>
- Habermas, J. (1996). *Between facts and norms. Contributions to a Discourse Theory of Law and Democracy*. The MIT Press.
- Heeks, R. (2021). Conceptualising digital justice, fairness and rights in development: Agenda-setting. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 87(4), e12191.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/isd2.12191>
- Held, V. (2006). *The ethics of care: Personal, political, and global*. Oxford University Press.
- Hickey, S., & Mohan, G. (Eds.). (2004). *Participation: From tyranny to transformation? Exploring new approaches to participation in development*. Zed Books.
- Kim, S. Y. (2018). Confucianism and Asian values: A reconsideration. *Philosophy Compass*, 13(2), e12479. <https://doi.org/10.1111/phc3.12479>
- Kimmerer, R. W. (2013). *Braiding sweetgrass: Indigenous wisdom, scientific knowledge and the teachings of plants*. Milkweed Editions.
- Kohn, M. (2019). *Colonialism*. Polity Press.
- Mamdani, M. (1996). *Citizen and subject: Contemporary Africa and the legacy of late colonialism*. Princeton University Press.
- Mariátegui, J. C. (2007). *7 Ensayos De Interpretación de la Realidad Peruana*. Fundacion Biblioteca Ayacucho (Original work published 1928).
- Mbembe, A. (2001). *On the postcolony*. University of California Press.
- Micciarelli G. & D'Andrea, M. (2020). Music, Art, the Power and the Capital: a Theoretical Proposal for an Income of Creativity and Care. In De Tullio M.F. (ed). *Commons Between Dreams and Reality*. Creative Industry.
- Mignolo, W. D. (2011). *The darker side of Western modernity: Global futures, decolonial options*. Duke University Press.
- Mignolo, W. D., & Walsh, C. E. (2018). *On decoloniality: Concepts, analytics, praxis*. Duke University Press.
- Murithi, T. (2006). Practical peacemaking wisdom from Africa: Reflections on Ubuntu. *The Journal of Pan African Studies*, 1(4), 25–34.
- Noble, S. U. (2018). *Algorithms of oppression: How search engines reinforce racism*. NYU Press.
- Nussbaum, M. C. (2000). *Women and human development: The capabilities approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nussbaum, M. C. (2011). *Creating capabilities: The human development approach*. Harvard University Press.

- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the Commons. The evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge University Press.
- Rawls, J. (1971). *A theory of justice*. Harvard University Press.
- Roberts, J. T., & Parks, B. C. (2007). *A climate of injustice: Global inequality, North–South politics, and climate policy*. MIT Press.
- Samuels, H. (2013). Feminist Legal Theory. In Banakar, R., & Travers, M. (Eds.). *Law and Social Theory*. Hart Publishing.
- Santos, B. de S. (2014). *Epistemologies of the South: Justice against epistemicide*. Routledge.
- Schlosberg, D. (2013). Theorising environmental justice: The expanding sphere of a discourse. *Environmental Politics*, 22(1), 37–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2013.755387>
- Schlosberg, D., & Collins, L. B. (2014). From environmental to climate justice: Climate change and the discourse of environmental justice. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 5(3), 359–374. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.275>
- Sen, A. (2009). *The idea of justice*. Harvard University Press.
- Smith, L. T. (2012). *Decolonizing methodologies: Research and indigenous peoples* (2nd ed.). Zed Books.
- Tandon, R. (2008). Participatory research: Revisiting the roots. *Mosaic*, 1(2), 1–9.
- Tronto, J. C. (1993). *Moral boundaries: A political argument for an ethic of care*. Routledge.
- Tuck, E., & Yang, K. W. (2012). Decolonization is not a metaphor. *Decolonization: Indigeneity, Education & Society*, 1(1), 1–40.
- Uvin, P. (2007). From the right to development to the rights-based approach: How ‘human rights’ entered development. *Development in Practice*, 17(4–5), 597–606. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614520701469617>
- Venditto, B., & Kamwanyah, N. J. (2025). Green Energy or Green Colonialism? The Case of Green Hydrogen in Namibia. *Nuovi Autoritarismi E Democrazie: Diritto, Istituzioni, Società (NAD-DIS)*, 7(1), 167–183. <https://doi.org/10.54103/2612-6672/28852>
- Whyte, K. (2016). Is it colonial déjà vu? Indigenous peoples and climate injustice. In J. Adamson & M. Davis (Eds.), *Humanities for the environment* (pp. 88–104). Routledge.
- Whyte, K. (2018). Settler colonialism, ecology, and environmental injustice. *Environment and Society*, 9(1), 125–144. <https://doi.org/10.3167/ares.2018.090109>
- Wiredu, K. (1996). *Cultural universals and particulars: An African perspective*. Indiana University Press.
- Young, I. M. (1990). *Justice and the politics of difference*. Princeton University Press
- Young, I. M. (2000). *Inclusion and Democracy*. Oxford University Press.